

STUDIES ON LIPASE FROM OIL SEEDS. PART XII. EFFECT OF HYDROGEN ION CONCENTRATION AND THE NATURE OF THE BUFFER ON THE HYDROLYSIS OF AMYL BUTYRATE BY RICINUS LIPASE FROM CASTOR SEED

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Hydrolysis of amyl butyrate by ricinus lipase was carried out using different buffer solutions of varying p_H in order to study the effect of hydrogen-ion concentration and the nature of the buffer on the enzymic hydrolysis of esters.

Ramakrishnan and Nevgi (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 7, 331, 332) studied in detail the hydrolysis of different aliphatic esters belonging to a homologous series using acetone-dried lipase from castor seed and ether solvent and found in the case of amyl butyrate, the maximum percentage hydrolysis of 31.2% on the 4th day.

The effect of hydrogen-ion concentration and the nature of the buffer on the enzymic hydrolysis of *n*-amyl butyrate were studied using different buffer mixtures of varying p_H .

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The acetone-dried sample of the lipase was prepared from fresh well ripened castor seed by Ramakrishnan and Nevgi's method (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1950, Science issue) and used for the experiment. Disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer mixtures of different p_H were prepared according to McIlvaine's method (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1923, 49, 183) and sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid and sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer mixtures of different p_H according to Walpole's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 195, 2501, 2521).

The hydrolysis of amyl butyrate by acetone-dried lipase was carried out at different p_H using different buffer mixtures.

Each set of the experiments consisted of 0.018 g. mol. of ester solution, 1 g. of acetone-dried lipase, 10 c.c. of ether solvent, 5 c.c. of buffer of varying p_H value and a few drops of toluene in a conical flask. It was corked and shaken well and incubated at 37°. Always a blank accompanied each sample. Necessary precautions were taken to take readings under sterile conditions. At different intervals of time, 1 c.c. portion was taken and 25 c.c. of neutral alcohol added, warmed for some time and titrated against $N/10$ -sodium hydroxide. From the the difference in readings between the sample and the blank, the percentage hydrolysis was calculated. The results are given in the following tables.

TABLE I

Optimum p_H using disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer.

p_H .	Percentage hydrolysis on the					
	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.
2.4	8.6	11.5	13.9	18.1	16.5	12.5
2.8	10.3	13.8	15.2	21.6	18.2	15.2
3.1	13.9	15.2	19.8	25.6	24.3	20.1
4.8	28.3	35.6	39.8	45.6	32.8	26.5
5.2	22.5	28.7	31.9	35.4	28.6	25.1
5.5	20.9	23.8	29.7	33.5	25.7	24.2
5.7	15.8	18.2	23.4	28.9	26.1	24.0
6.2	10.9	14.8	19.1	24.3	18.1	15.4

TABLE II

Optimum p_H using sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid buffer.

p_H	Percentage hydrolysis on the					
	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.
1.5	10.1	14.3	15.8	17.5	14.9	12.3
2.9	13.5	15.8	17.5	19.1	18.7	15.6
3.8	15.1	18.4	22.1	25.6	23.8	21.9
4.3	17.2	23.1	25.6	29.3	27.8	22.5
4.8	20.8	25.3	30.2	35.8	31.6	28.7
5.2	19.1	22.8	25.6	29.5	28.3	25.6
5.5	18.1	20.1	22.8	25.6	23.9	21.8
5.7	15.3	18.1	20.9	23.9	21.6	18.7
6.0	13.8	15.6	18.7	21.8	20.9	18.0

TABLE III

Optimum p_H using sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer.

p_H	Percentage hydrolysis on the					
	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.
3.8	9.1	11.5	15.6	17.8	15.2	13.9
4.1	10.8	14.2	18.0	19.9	17.5	15.8
4.8	14.3	17.5	22.8	28.7	25.6	22.3
4.9	15.8	20.6	25.3	31.8	27.2	24.8
5.5	14.1	17.6	20.1	25.6	22.8	20.9
5.7	12.8	15.5	19.8	22.6	20.1	18.7
5.9	10.2	13.8	15.6	17.8	16.1	15.8
6.0	9.1	11.2	13.8	15.6	12.1	8.9

From the above tables, it is found that the optimum p_H for enzymic hydrolysis of amyl butyrate is 4.8 in case of disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer, 4.8 in the case of sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid buffer and 4.9 in the case of sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer. It can be seen that the optimum p_H for the hydrolysis of esters by ricinus lipase slightly varies *i. e.*, 4.8 to 4.9 p_H with the nature of the buffer used. But at the same time, the maximum percentage hydrolysis reached is the greatest in case of disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer and the least in sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer. Generally, in all cases, the percentage hydrolysis reaches the maximum on the 4th day.

Thus, it is inferred that the enzymic hydrolysis of the ester depends upon the hydrogen-ion concentration, the nature of the buffer used and the time of reaction.

It can be seen that disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer is good for synthesis as well as for the hydrolysis of esters.

Further work is under progress to study the effect of the buffer concentration and enzyme concentration on the hydrolysis of esters by lipase.